
The Effect of Treatment Sewage Sludge Applied to the Vetch + Barley Mixture on Soil Heavy Metal Content

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Abstract This study was conducted in the trial fields of Ege University Faculty of Agriculture in Bornova in 2015 and 2016 in order to determine the effect of treated sewage sludge (SST) applied to vetch + barley mixture on the heavy metal content of the soil. The study was carried out in a randomized complete block design with four replications and 1, 2 and 3 t/da of sewage sludge were applied in addition to control and mineral fertilizer applications. In the study the heavy metals of soil such as copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb) and chromium (Cr) contents were investigated. As a result of the research, although slight increases were found in Cu, Mn, Ni, Zn, Cd contents, these increases were observed to be below the limit values of the regulation of the use of sewage sludge in agriculture. Applications had no significant effect on available K and available Mn. When the results are according to the soil analysis results and heavy metal amounts from the sewage sludge, it is concluded that 2 t da⁻¹ sewage sludge can be used in vetch + barley mixtures.

Keywords Heavy metal, soil, vetch + barley mixture

1. Introduction

Today, one of the biggest problems of municipalities is the disposal of sewage sludge from urban and industrial treatment systems [1]. Various projects are carried out for the recycling of sewage sludge in many countries, and the most important of these is the utilization of stabilized wastes in agricultural areas [2]. Although the use of sewage sludge in farming is thought suitable because of high organic matter, macro and micro nutrients, it is fact that they can cause some side effects on soil and plant for their heavy metals [3-4]. Soil pollution caused by the use of sewage sludge has become a serious problem for the world [5]. Heavy metal presence in sewage sludge used as agricultural fertilizer is a major problem for soil and product quality. Therefore, it should be used carefully and limit values should not be exceeded. Sewage sludge contains some nutrients and organic substances and can be used instead of commercial fertilizers for the plant [6].

The use of treatment sludge in agriculture by removing the harmful aspects is known as a common practice in the world [7-9]. The rate of using sewage sludge as fertilizer varies between 10% and 80% in European countries. What makes it possible to use sewage sludge as fertilizers is that it contains macro and micro plant nutrients in addition to high organic matter. However, if sewage sludge is to be used as a fertilizer, considering that it may contain toxic substances and disease factors, these values should be under the limits of the laws and regulations [10-11]. The sludge used in agriculture in developed countries is subjected to various processes such as composting to reduce its negative effects. In addition, wastewater sludges are analyzed in detail and their content is determined [12-14]. It is stated that the low heavy metal content in soil and plants as a result of using sewage sludge was due to the low bioavailability of the sewage sludge [15]. In a study where chemical fertilizers and sewage sludge were given to winter wheat, it was reported that sludge increased the yield of

wheat and the nutrients of the grain [16]. It is announced that the application of sewage sludge in agricultural areas is a widely accepted method and it is necessary to be careful in terms of heavy metal levels as well as increasing productivity [17]. It is reported that Cd, Cu, Zn concentrations increased significantly in corn treated with sewage sludge [18]. It was announced that the treatment sludge used as a fertilizer in sunflower caused a significant increase in heavy metal contents in the soil [19]. This study was conducted to determine the effect of mineral fertilizer and various sewage sludge doses on the heavy metal content of the soil in a mixture of common vetch + barley.

2. Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in the experimental areas of Ege University, Faculty of Agriculture, Dept. of Field Crops for two years between 2015-2017. In the study, treated sewage sludge with 90% dry matter content obtained from the Waste Water Treatment Plant of Izmir Metropolitan Municipality was used as a material. Some properties of sewage sludge are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Some physical and chemical properties and plant nutrient content of the soil sample taken from the trial area

Feature	Unit	Value
pH		7.18
Electrical conductivity	$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$	1945
Organic matter	%	51.20
Organic carbon	%	29.66
Lime	%	5.35
Total N	%	2.99
Total P	%	0.2275
Total K	%	0.34
Calcium (Ca)	%	6.36
Magnesium (Mg)	%	2.04
Sodium (Na)	mg kg^{-1}	1390.5
Fe	mg kg^{-1}	12754.96
Cu	mg kg^{-1}	176.5
Zn	mg kg^{-1}	1376.59
Mn	mg kg^{-1}	350
Nickel (Ni)	mg kg^{-1}	69.73
Lead (Pb)	mg kg^{-1}	17.44
Chromium (Cr)	mg kg^{-1}	112.53
Cadmium (Cd)	mg kg^{-1}	2.83

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that the sewage sludge used has high organic matter content and its heavy metal values are below the limit values specified in the "sludge using regulations in Soil" [20]. As a result of microbiological analysis of sewage sludge, the fecal coli level that will limit its use has not been determined. The plant material of the study was composed of Alper common vetch (*Vicia sativa* L.) variety and Sancak barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) variety obtained from Aegean Agricultural Research Institute. Some physical and chemical properties of the soil sample taken from the research area before the trials are established are given in Table 2. The soil of the research area has a clay loam texture and is slightly alkaline. Organic matter content of the research soil, which has no salinity, is low, lime content is moderate, available P content is sufficient and available K content is very high. It was determined that the available Cu and Zn content of the soils was sufficient, the amount of Mn was low and the Fe content was moderate (Table 2).

Table 2: Analysis results of the sewage sludge used in the experiment

Soil property	Value	Method
Sand (%)	40.80	With body cylinder [21]
Clay (%)	34.94	
Silt (%)	24.26	
pH	7.51	Saturation paste [22]
Electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	920	Saturation paste [22]
Organic matter (%)	1.17	Modifiye Walkley-Black [22]
Lime (%)	9.9	Volumetric [23]
Total N (%)	0.094	Modified Kjeldahl [24]
Available P (mg kg^{-1})	21.1	extracted with 21.1 0.5 N NaH_2CO_3 (pH: 8.5) [25]
Available K (mg kg^{-1})	352	
Available Ca (mg kg^{-1})	6875	extraction with 1 N NH_4OAc (pH: 7.0) [26]
Available Na (mg kg^{-1})	30.8	
Available Mg (mg kg^{-1})	304.2	
Available Fe (mg kg^{-1})	4.39	
Available Mn (mg kg^{-1})	7.58	DTPA (diethylenetriamine pentaacetic acid) (pH: 7.3) [27]
Available Zn (mg kg^{-1})	1.38	
Available Cu (mg kg^{-1})	1.66	

In the research, randomly complete blocks design with four replications was used. In the study in addition to control and mineral fertilizer applications 10, 20 and 30 t ha⁻¹ doses of treated sewage sludge were used. In the plots where traditional fertilizer application was made, fertilization was made according to the results of the soil analysis and 15-15-15 compound fertilizers was applied into the soil as 6 kg da⁻¹ N, P₂O₅ and K₂O before sowing in the plots where sewage sludge was applied, sewage sludge was mixed with the soil according to the determined doses before sowing. In the research, sowing was made in the plots having 20 cm row spacing and 10 rows. Plot size was 2 m x 5 m = 10 m². Seeds of vetch and barley were hand-planted together in the same rows in a rate of 15 kg da⁻¹ vetch (75%) and 5 kg da⁻¹ barley [28-29]. Sowing was carried out on 08.12.2015 and on 12.12.2016 in first and second years. Weed control was hand by made. At the end of the study, soil samples were taken from each plot at a depth of 0-20 cm with a stainless steel shovel in accordance with the general rules [22] Heavy metal (Cu, Zn, Mn, Ni, Cd, Pb, Cr) analyzes were made in the soil samples and the soil properties was investigated in terms of sludge applications. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17 (SPSS 17.0 2008). Differences between means were found by LSD test $P \leq 0.05$ [30].

3. Results

Copper (Cu), zinc (Zn) and manganese (Mn)

Results regarding the effects of the applications on Cu, Zn and Mn content of the soil are shown in Table 3. As can be seen in Table 3, Cu and Mn content in the first year and Zn content in both years were affected at $p < 0.01$ level. Applications affected Cu content at $p < 0.05$ level significantly in the second year. No significant effect on Mn content was observed in the second year of the applications (Table 3).

Table 3: The effect of the applications on the Cu, Zn and Mn content of soil (mg kg^{-1})

Application	Cu		Zn		Mn	
	2015	2016	2015	2016	2015	2016
Control	24.71 b	27.51 bc	134.10 bc	122.40 c	57.90 b	69.45
10 t ha ⁻¹ SST	31.00 a	24.58 c	151.67 ab	142.50 b	92.70 a	90.95
20 t ha ⁻¹ SST	33.59 a	26.27 c	185.75 a	179.60 a	103.75 a	84.20
30 t ha ⁻¹ SST	20.39 c	33.09a	96.39 cd	106.40 d	108.87 a	77.25
Mineral fertilizers	20.09 c	32.65 ab	82.47 d	89.34 e	54.10 b	65.87
LSD 0.05:	**	*	**	**	**	n.s.

** : Significant difference at $p < 0.01$ level, ns: Not significant, * Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level. The difference between the averages shown by different letters in the same column is significant

In the first year the highest Cu contents were obtained as 33.59 and 31.00 mg kg⁻¹ with sewage sludge applications of 20 t ha⁻¹ and 10 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Mineral fertilizer and 30 t ha⁻¹ sludge application gave the lowest Cu contents as 20.09- 20.39 mg kg⁻¹, respectively and these contents were in the same statistic group. In the second year, the highest Cu content was obtained as 33.09 mg kg⁻¹ from 30 t ha⁻¹ sludge application, while 10 t ha⁻¹ and 20 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge gave lower Cu contents as 24.58 and 26.27 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. In the first year, the highest zinc was obtained as 185.75 mg kg⁻¹ from 20 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge, while the lowest value was obtained from mineral fertilizer application with 82.47 mg kg⁻¹. In the second year, similar to the first year the highest Zn content (179.60 mg kg⁻¹) was taken with 20 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge application. Mineral fertilizer gave the lowest Zn content (89.34 mg kg⁻¹). The first year the highest Mn contents were obtained from 10, 20 and 30 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge applications among 92.70-108.87 mg kg⁻¹. Control and mineral fertilizer applications gave the lowest Mn contents as 57.90 and 54.10 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. Second year Mn contents varied between 65.87 mg kg⁻¹ and 90.95 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 3).

Nickel (Ni) and cadmium (Cd)

Results regarding the effects of the applications on Ni and Cd content of the soil are shown in Table 4. In terms of the Ni content were found statistically significant at level of $p < 0.01$ in the first year, but no significant difference was found in the second year. Cd content was affected significantly at $p < 0.05$ level in the second year, while no significant effect was observed in the first year (Table 4).

Table 4: The effect of the applications on Ni and Cd content of the soil (mg kg⁻¹)

Application	Ni		Cd	
	2015	2016	2015	2016
Control	54.13A	60.39	1.30	1.35 ab
10 t ha ⁻¹ SST	54.41A	59.78	1.39	1.31 b
20 t ha ⁻¹ SST	54.33A	61.12	1.48	1.33 b
30 t ha ⁻¹ SST	47.78B	61.20	1.28	1.42 a
Mineral fertilizers	46.67B	61.55	1.28	1.43 a
LSD 0.05:	**	n.s.	n.s.	*

** : Significant difference at $p < 0.01$ level, ns: Not significant, * Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level. The difference between the averages shown by different letters in the same column is significant

In the first year, the highest Ni contents were obtained from 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹ sludge applications and control as 54.41, 54.33 and 54.13 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. These three applications were the same statistical group. The lowest Ni contents were 47.78 and 46.67 mg kg⁻¹ from 30 t ha⁻¹ sludge application and mineral fertilizer application, respectively. In the second year, Ni contents changed among 59.78 mg kg⁻¹ and 61.55 mg kg⁻¹. Cadmium content varied among 1.28-1.39 mg kg⁻¹ in the first year. In the second year the highest Cd contents were obtained from mineral fertilizer and 30 tons of sewage sludge application as 1.43 and 1.42 mg kg⁻¹ respectively, while the lowest Cd contents were obtained from 20 and 10 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge applications as 1.33 and 1.31 mg kg⁻¹, respectively (Table 4).

Lead (Pb) and Chrome (Cr)

Results regarding the effects of the applications on Pb and Cr content of the soil are shown in Table 5. The both Pb and Cr contents were affected from the applications at $p < 0.01$ level in the first year. In the second year they were affected from the applications at $p < 0.05$ statistic level (Table 5).

Table 5: The effect of the applications on the Pb and Cr content of the soil (mg kg⁻¹)

Application	Pb		Cr	
	2015	2016	2015	2016
Control	30.35 b	45.16 ab	40.49 b	43.60 bc
10 t ha ⁻¹ SST	38.00 a	41.97 b	44.15 b	41.63 c
20 t ha ⁻¹ SST	39.72 a	42.13 b	51.48 a	42.39 c
30 t ha ⁻¹ SST	24.06 c	50.25 a	30.44 c	47.05 ab
Mineral fertilizers	23.44 c	51.00 a	29.97 c	49.15 a
LSD 0.05:	**	*	**	*

** : Significant difference at $p < 0.01$ level, * Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level. The difference between the averages shown by different letters in the same column is significant

In the first year, the highest Pb contents were 39.72 and 38.00 mg kg⁻¹, respectively from 20t ha⁻¹ and 10 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge applications. The lowest Pb contents were obtained from 30 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge and mineral fertilizer application as 24.06 and 23.44 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. In the second year, the highest Pb contents were taken from mineral fertilizer and 30 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge applications as 51.00 and 50.25 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. The lowest Pb contents were taken from sewage sludge applications of 20 t ha⁻¹ and 10 t ha⁻¹ as 42.13 and 41.97 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. Regarding the Cr content, the first year 20 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge gave the highest Cr content (51.48mg kg⁻¹), whereas 30 t ha⁻¹ sludge and mineral fertilizer application gave the lowest Cr contents as 30.44 and 29.97 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. In the second year, the highest Cr content was 49.15 mg kg⁻¹ from mineral fertilizer application, while the control, 10 t ha⁻¹ and 20 t ha⁻¹ sewage sludge applications gave the lowest Cr content.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Although it is reported that sewage sludges contain high amounts of organic matter, as well as many macro and micro nutrients required by plants [31], it is accepted by many researchers that their unconscious use causes heavy metal increase in the soil [32-33-34-35]. Many studies with sewage sludge show that different doses of sludge have different effects on the heavy metal content of the soil [36-32]. In our study, the increase in Cu, Ni, Pb and Cr in the first year and Zn in both years with the increase of amount of sewage sludge, but decrease with 30 t ha⁻¹ sludge application are similar to the results of these researchers. In Demir and Cimrin studies investigating the effect of treatment sludge and humic acid on maize, stated that Cd and Pb contents increased with increase the sewage sludge. On the other hand they found that Ni and Co contents increased until 20% sludge and decreased at 30 % sludge level. So, they supported our results with these findings. Although there are many studies showing that sewage sludge increases the heavy metal content of the soil, there are many studies showing that these increases do not contain heavy metals at a level that will limit sludge use [37]. As a matter of fact, [38-37-39], stated that the toxicity limits for heavy metals in the soil were not reached with sewage sludge doses as a result of their studies. There are studies showing that not only sewage sludge but also some fertilizers such as mineral and barn manure used cause the increase in heavy metal content of soils. [40], reported that manure increased the Cd amount in barn manure studies, [41] also stated that various NPK mineral fertilizer doses increase the amount of Pb and Cd in the soil. The fact that Cu, Cd and Pb contents were higher than 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹ sludge applications in mineral fertilizer applications and the Cr content was higher than all other applications in the second year of our study were paralleled with these researchers' findings. The results obtained in the study showed that sewage sludge caused an increase in the heavy metal content of the soil. However, these increases were not at a level that would limit the use of sewage sludge. Although it is seen that there is no toxicity problem related to the period when the used sludge was obtained, it should be kept in mind that sewage sludge can accumulate in the soil and cause toxic effects on plants and other living creatures in case of continuous application. When the results are evaluated in general, it is concluded that 2 t ha⁻¹ treatment sludge can be used according to the soil analysis results of soil.

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